

Research Questionnaire

Dear Respondent,

You are invited to participate in a research study that aims to examine how hotel green practices influence willingness to pay, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty in star-rated hotels.

Your insights are valuable in contributing to academic research in the hospitality sector. Your responses will remain strictly confidential and will be used solely for academic purposes. Participation is voluntary, and you may withdraw at any time.

Thank you for your time and cooperation.

Ethical Disclaimer

This study follows the ethical guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki. All participants are adults aged 18 years and above, participating voluntarily in an anonymous and non-invasive survey.

Consent

I have read the information above and voluntarily agree to participate in this study.

Instructions: Please indicate your level of agreement:

1 = Strongly Disagree | 2 = Disagree | 3 = Neutral | 4 = Agree | 5 = Strongly Agree

SECTION A: Demographic Information

1. Age: _____
2. Gender: Male Female Other
3. Purpose of Stay: Leisure Business Other
4. Type of Room Stayed: Standard Deluxe Suite
5. Duration of Stay (Nights): _____

SECTION B: Hotel Green Practices (HGP)

HGP1. This hotel makes substantial efforts to reduce energy consumption (e.g., LED lighting, smart thermostats).

1 2 3 4 5

HGP2. This hotel has an active program to reduce water use (e.g., low-flow faucets, linen reuse).

1 2 3 4 5

HGP3. This hotel minimizes waste by recycling and composting.

1 2 3 4 5

HGP4. This hotel offers environmentally friendly amenities (e.g., bulk dispensers, eco-certified toiletries).

1 2 3 4 5

SECTION C: Willingness to Pay (WTP)

WTP1. I am willing to pay a higher price for a room in this green hotel compared to a regular one.

1 ■ 2 ■ 3 ■ 4 ■ 5 ■

WTP2. I would accept higher room rates if environmentally friendly practices are guaranteed.

1 ■ 2 ■ 3 ■ 4 ■ 5 ■

WTP3. I would pay more, if necessary, to stay in a hotel that is environmentally responsible.

1 ■ 2 ■ 3 ■ 4 ■ 5 ■

SECTION D: Customer Loyalty (CL)

CL1. I intend to stay in this hotel again in the future.

1 ■ 2 ■ 3 ■ 4 ■ 5 ■

CL2. I will recommend this hotel to friends and relatives.

1 ■ 2 ■ 3 ■ 4 ■ 5 ■

CL3. If I need accommodation in this area, this hotel would be my first choice.

1 ■ 2 ■ 3 ■ 4 ■ 5 ■

CL4. I would say positive things about this hotel to others.

1 ■ 2 ■ 3 ■ 4 ■ 5 ■

SECTION E: Customer Satisfaction (CS)

CS1. I am happy with my decision to stay here because of its environmental practices.

1 ■ 2 ■ 3 ■ 4 ■ 5 ■

CS2. I am pleased with the hotel's eco-friendly products/services.

1 ■ 2 ■ 3 ■ 4 ■ 5 ■

CS3. Overall, I feel satisfied with the hotel's environmental performance.

1 ■ 2 ■ 3 ■ 4 ■ 5 ■

CS4. My decision to choose this hotel was influenced by its green image.

1 ■ 2 ■ 3 ■ 4 ■ 5 ■

Additional Comments:
